

How am I going? Behavioral engagement mediates the effect of individual feedback on writing performance

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ABSTRACT

Background: Successful feedback should provide learning goals, evaluate current performance and indicate improvement strategies. Furthermore, feedback can only positively affect student performance if students actively engage with it. Thus, it is necessary to consider the feedback reception process in addition to the feedback information itself.

Aims: This study compares the effects of different types of feedback information on the writing performance of lower secondary students of English as a foreign language (EFL) in a digital learning environment. Behavioral engagement was considered as a mediator of the feedback effect.

Sample: Participants were $N = 338$ eighth- and ninth-grade EFL students (54.7% female) enrolled in lower-secondary education within the Swiss school system.

Methods: We conducted a web-based randomized-controlled experiment, in which students were randomly assigned to four conditions receiving varying amounts of rubric-based feedback information. We used log data (time on feedback page) as a proxy for their behavioral engagement with the feedback.

Results: Even though writing performance improved substantially across conditions, there were no differential effects of the type of feedback information on performance. However, EFL learners who received individual performance information spent more time with the feedback, especially those with low prior achievement. Mediation analysis showed that the effectiveness of the feedback was mediated by the time spent on the feedback as an indicator of students' behavioral engagement.

Conclusions: Advantages for individual performance feedback over more general information were observed as a function of time spent with the feedback. This finding implies that engagement should be considered in feedback research.

Writing is an essential and multifaceted skill (Graham, 2019; Hayes, 2012) necessary across various settings, from the home (Freedman et al., 2016) to the classroom (Bangert-Drowns et al., 2004; Graham & Hebert, 2011) to the workplace (Light, 2001). Therefore, deficiencies in writing skills can impede one's progress in personal, academic, and professional areas (Graham, 2006). It is a fundamental goal of education systems around the globe to equip students with the necessary writing skills. Nevertheless, findings indicate that not all students meet this objective (Graham & Rijlaarsdam, 2016; National Center for Educational

Statistics, 2012), which is even more challenging when we consider writing in a second or foreign language (Keller et al., 2020; Hyland, 2008).

Prior research on the effects of feedback on students' (writing) performance has shown heterogeneous findings (Graham et al., 2015; Scherer et al., 2024; Wisniewski et al., 2020). Possible explanations for this are (a) different conceptualizations of feedback, resulting in different types of information presented to the students (Mertens et al., 2022); (b) interindividual differences between students (Fyfe, 2016;

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Mertens et al., 2022); and (c) the mediating role of internal processes like the ability and willingness to engage with feedback (Fong, 2023; Mandouit & Hattie, 2023). In particular, the relationship between feedback features, student perceptions as potential mediators, and the likelihood of students' feedback implementation needs to be considered in detail (Wu & Schunn, 2020). This study intends to contribute to these issues by focusing on the effectiveness of different kinds of feedback information and the role of behavioral engagement with the feedback in the context of learning English as a foreign language (EFL). Furthermore, we take individual prerequisites of EFL learners that potentially interact with feedback effects into account.

In their feedback model, Hattie and Timperley (2007) presented three questions that successful feedback needs to answer: (1) Where am I going? (transparency of learning goals); (2) How am I going? (individual performance information); (3) Where to next? (individual performance improvement information). Empirical evidence suggests that successful feedback should answer all three questions, with the third being the most relevant one (Hattie et al., 2021; Wollenschläger et al., 2015). To test this assumption, we systematically investigate the incremental value of the three types of information using rubric-based feedback for EFL writing.

Prior knowledge of the domain has been shown to moderate feedback effectiveness. Feedback has typically yielded larger effect sizes for learners with low prior knowledge than for learners with high prior knowledge, especially concerning higher-order learning outcomes (Mertens et al., 2022; Sitzman et al., 2015). Even though the population in this study – lower secondary EFL learners likely without substantial previous instruction or practice opportunities on the topic – would be considered as possessing relatively low prior knowledge concerning the task in general, there might be differences in the degree to which students benefit from feedback. To further differentiate between learners and better understand which type of feedback is effective for whom, we consider students' domain-specific achievement by incorporating their previous English grades as an individual moderator of feedback effects.

Research has shown that feedback can be most beneficial for student learning if students actively engage with it on a cognitive, affective, and behavioral level (Lipnevich & Panadero, 2021; Zhang & Hyland, 2018). Thus, it is necessary to consider the feedback reception process in addition to the feedback information itself. In this study, we therefore considered time spent with the feedback as an indicator of behavioral engagement and a mediator of feedback effectiveness.

1. Theoretical background

1.1. Feedback effectiveness

Individualized feedback is widely regarded as a key determinant in student learning outcomes. This assertion is supported by empirical evidence ($d = 0.64$; Hattie, 2022) and aligns with teachers' professional beliefs (Fleckenstein et al., 2015). Specifically for feedback on writing, a meta-analysis by Graham et al. (2015) revealed that the impact of feedback varies, with effect sizes ranging from $d = 0.38$ to $d = 0.87$, depending on the feedback source. Recent meta-analyses on the effectiveness of computer-based writing feedback have found effect sizes ranging from $g = 0.55$ to $g = 0.86$ (Fleckenstein et al., 2023; Ngo et al., 2022; Zhai & Ma, 2022). Differentiating for the type of language learner and level of outcome, Scherer et al. (2024) found a mean effect ($g = 0.53$) of algorithmic feedback on foreign language learners' surface-level writing outcomes but a non-significant effect ($g = -0.07$) on deep-level writing outcomes. The heterogeneous meta-analytic findings show that (computer-based) feedback on writing is a promising support measure to improve students' performance – however, its effectiveness depends on various aspects.

Feedback positively affects the performance of learners, especially when it is provided in close temporal proximity, explains the gap between current task performance and the learning objective, reduces

cognitive load, is task-specific and elaborate (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996; Mory, 2004; Shute, 2008). A recent meta-analysis of the effects of different types of feedback information on learning across domains has found that most studies target lower-order learning, like recall tasks in multiple-choice tests (Mertens et al., 2022). However, such results do not directly apply to higher-order tasks like writing a text. Feedback-related research in writing has mainly concentrated on the overarching effect of feedback without considering how different feedback components influence its effectiveness (Graham, 2018). The assumption from Hattie and Timperley's (2007) model that effective feedback should integrate three types of information remains largely unexplored regarding complex writing tasks in lower secondary education.

As for many other domains, digital learning environments can enhance students' writing skills, as providing timely feedback on a given task is one of the great potentials of technology-assisted learning. However, feedback design in digital learning environments is seldom based on empirical evidence (Narciss, 2018). This may be partly due to inconsistent research findings regarding feedback effectiveness (Fleckenstein et al., 2023; Fyfe & Rittle-Johnson, 2016; Shute, 2008). The degree to which students can benefit from feedback depends on several internal (e.g., prior knowledge, feedback engagement) and external (e.g., type of feedback information) factors, which need to be carefully considered when designing effective feedback (Lipnevich & Smith, 2022).

1.2. The role of prior knowledge

Prior knowledge is considered a relevant factor that influences how learners process feedback (e.g., Fyfe et al., 2012; Mory, 2004; Narciss & Huth, 2004), which, in turn, can impact subsequent performance (Sitzman et al., 2014, 2015). Learners with high prior knowledge can draw on an existing semantic network, which helps them to integrate new information from feedback more effectively (Clariana & Koul, 2005; Sitzman et al., 2015). Fyfe and Rittle-Johnson (2015) showed that learners with low prior knowledge benefited from evaluative feedback, while learners with high prior knowledge were even negatively affected by feedback. Instead, the latter benefited from problem-solving without feedback. Thus, avoiding redundant information may be advisable, especially for learners with high prior knowledge.

In their recent meta-analysis, Mertens et al. (2022) found that computer-based feedback yielded larger effect sizes for learners with low prior knowledge than for learners with high prior knowledge. For higher-order learning outcomes, more informative feedback types (e.g., elaborated feedback) were most effective for learners with low prior knowledge. For learners with high prior knowledge, more simplistic types of feedback (e.g., knowledge of correct response) were equally effective; however, effect sizes were generally smaller. These findings indicate that feedback may be more beneficial for learners with low prior knowledge than for learners with high prior knowledge, especially when it provides relevant information for performance improvement.

1.3. (Behavioral) engagement with feedback

The effect of feedback on learning is affected by behavioral variables (Narciss & Huth, 2004; Schwartz & White, 2000; Shute, 2008). The topics of feedback receptivity and feedback engagement have recently gained increasing attention (Lipnevich & Lopera-Oquendo, 2022; Zhang & Hyland, 2018). The basic assumption behind this research is that feedback can only affect student performance positively if students actively engage with it on a cognitive, affective, and behavioral level (Lipnevich et al., 2021).

Learners' engagement is crucial for learning processes in general. It refers to the extent to which students are involved in learning activities (Kuh, 2001) and is assumed to positively impact students' academic achievement (Wang & Holcombe, 2010). Learning engagement can be

influenced by feedback and, in turn, affect students' performance on a certain task (Butler & Winne, 1995; Grawemeyer et al., 2017; Wang & Zhang, 2020). Studies show that active engagement of learners is essential to learning from feedback (Handley et al., 2011; Winstone et al., 2017). Thus, engagement can be assumed to mediate the effect of feedback on student performance or learning.

Based on a characterization of learning engagement by Fredricks et al. (2004), Zhang and Hyland (2018) proposed a model to investigate students' engagement with feedback in the context of writing. The authors proposed feedback engagement to include three dimensions of behavioral, affective, and cognitive engagement. Behavioral engagement refers to students' overt reaction to feedback, such as reading it, asking for clarification, or revising their text. Affective engagement refers to students' emotional and attitudinal responses to feedback. Cognitive engagement refers to how students attend to feedback, depending on using cognitive (and metacognitive) strategies. In line with Handley et al. (2011), we assume that even though behavioral engagement with feedback is not the whole story, it is necessary for the feedback to be effective (Mayordomo et al., 2022). In online learning environments, behavioral engagement may refer to all actions or behaviors that students show in relation to feedback and that can typically be tracked using log data.

2. Present study

In the present study, we investigated the specific and incremental effects of certain types of feedback information on improving lower secondary students' EFL writing performance and engagement with the writing task in a digital learning environment. To our knowledge, no previous study has tested the effect of different kinds of feedback information in the context of EFL writing instruction in lower secondary education. For this purpose, we chose an experimental design that enabled us to investigate the specific effects of the feedback model by Hattie and Timperley (2007). As outlined above, the model proposes three questions that successful feedback needs to answer. These three questions correspond to different kinds of information that feedback can feature: (1) *transparency information* offers insight into the task-specific learning goals; (2) *individual performance information* evaluates the student's current task performance in relation to these learning goals; and (3) *individual performance improvement information* elaborates on what the student can do to close the gap between current and target performance. In our study, we compared different feedback conditions by presenting the different types of feedback information in a cumulative way, which enabled an investigation of the incremental effect of each specific kind of feedback information. Additionally, we investigated if and how prior achievement (as operationalized by the previous English grade) moderated the effect of the feedback intervention.

We also investigated whether behavioral engagement mediates the feedback effect, assuming that feedback can affect student performance best if the student actively engages. Digital learning environments offer the opportunity to collect process data, which can be used as behavioral measures of feedback engagement. Thus, we used log data to measure the time students spent on the feedback page as a proxy for their behavioral engagement with the feedback. We expected the effect of feedback on students' performance improvement to be mediated by students' behavioral engagement with the feedback.

Building on Hattie and Timperley's (2007) feedback model, as well as the literature on feedback effects and engagement, we addressed the following research questions.

- 1) Does students' writing performance improve within a digital writing tool?

We expected writing performance to improve substantially from the first to the final task, independent of the condition students had been assigned to. Self-regulated writing practice with a digital tool should

positively impact students' writing performance, even without or with inferior individualized feedback.

- 2) What kind of feedback information leads to writing performance improvement and behavioral engagement?

According to Hattie and Timperley (2007), it is essential that feedback answers all three questions posed in the model; however, they consider individual performance improvement information to be the most relevant. Therefore, we assumed incremental effects of all three experimental conditions. Still, we expected to find the largest effect in Experimental Group 3 (EG3), which received specific information on how to improve their writing in the next step.

- 3) Does prior achievement moderate the effect of feedback on writing performance improvement and behavioral engagement?

Drawing on findings from meta-analytic research on prior knowledge moderating the effect of feedback on higher-order learning outcomes (Mertens et al., 2022), we expected low-achieving EFL students to benefit more strongly from feedback than high-achieving EFL students.

- 4) Does behavioral feedback engagement mediate the effect of feedback on performance improvement?

We expected the effect of feedback on performance improvement to be mediated by the extent to which students engaged with it on a behavioral level. Positive feedback effects are assumed to be stronger when students spend more time with the feedback.

3. Methods

The data for this study were collected as part of the project eRubric: "What makes feedback effective for whom? The interplay of instructional rubric use and individual student characteristics in foreign language learning." The project was funded by the Jacobs Foundation (grant number: 2019 1316 0) from 2019 to 2021 (Fleckenstein et al., 2020; Keller et al., 2023). This study is a computer-based intervention in which lower secondary students of English as a foreign language (EFL) received rubric-based feedback on three writing tasks (formal email request). In these tasks, they had to ask for information in an authentic situation while adhering to the conventions of a formal email. In total, students wrote three texts on different tasks of comparable design and difficulty, and feedback was provided after each text using a rubric specifically developed for this purpose (see Keller et al., 2023 for a detailed description of rubric development and validation). The rubric score on the initial writing task was used as the pre-measure of performance; the score on the final writing task was used as the post-measure. Performance improvement – the difference between initial and final performance – is compared between feedback conditions as the central outcome. The detailed methodological aspects of the intervention study are specified below.

3.1. Sample

In total, $N = 373$ eighth- and ninth-grade EFL students at eight lower secondary schools (ISCED level 2) in North-Western Switzerland (Canton Aargau) participated in the study. We excluded $n = 35$ learners who had not received any feedback on at least one of their texts. In most of these cases, no feedback was provided to the student because the rater had overlooked the text in the system (which had a rather complex rating interface) or due to a failed connection between the rating and the writing system. The final sample consisted of $N = 338$ students, $n = 185$ (54.7%) of which were female, $n = 139$ (41.1%) were male, $n = 6$ (1.8%) indicated non-binary gender, and $n = 8$ (2.4%) did not provide a response. The mean age was $M = 14.14$ ($SD = 0.88$), with 57.5% of the

students in eighth grade and 42.5% in ninth grade. In the canton of Aargau, students are allocated to one of three educational tracks at the end of primary school (i.e., after year 6) based on their grades: high-level track (*Bezirksschule*), mid-level track (*Sekundarschule*) or lower-level track (*Realschule*). Students in our sample attended either the mid-level track (58.1%) or the high-level track (41.9%). No students from the lower-level track were represented in the sample because no teachers volunteered to participate.

The study did not comprehensively survey students' socioeconomic, migration, and language backgrounds. However, we collected some information about the length of EFL instruction. All of the students had been learning English since primary school. Most students had started learning English in third grade (81.8%) or even before that (7.5%). 9.1% percent indicated to have started in fourth grade, 1.5% in fifth or sixth grade. This type of heterogeneity is typical for Switzerland, where the onset of English instruction differs between districts (cantons).

Power analysis using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2007) showed that a sample of $N = 311$ would yield a power of 0.70 for a small effect size of $f^2 = 0.02$ in a linear multiple regression model with eight predictors and fixed effects. Thus, the realized sample was large enough for a small effect to become significant at the 5%-level.

3.2. Procedure

The experiment was conducted using a web-based digital learning tool programmed with the software LimeSurvey. Participants navigated through a sequence of web pages one by one, each guiding them through the writing process. Students were presented with the tasks on the pages, wrote emails, and received feedback. In the end, students were asked to fill in a short questionnaire, including information on sociodemographic variables (age, gender), their EFL background, and their perception of the feedback. Even though the target language of the intervention was English, the instructional language of the tool (apart from the writing prompts) was German to ensure students' understanding.

The study took place in the classroom or the school computer lab during regular English classes. It was administered by two research team members, who made sure that the tool was functioning and that all students worked on and understood the tasks. Thus, treatment fidelity was rather high. The experiment took about 60 min in total, during which students were asked to respond to three very similar consecutive writing tasks (email writing prompts). Students were asked to write formal requests via email in English. In each task, they were presented with a writing prompt in which they had to request information in authentic, everyday contexts (asking for information about a language school, inquiring about a summer job, and collecting information about a campground). Each writing prompt contained source material and an indication of what information students should ask in the email. Writing time was limited to 12 min per writing prompt. The three writing prompts were identical in task composition and constraints, and the tasks were presented in randomized order to avoid sequence effects.

The genre of formal email writing was chosen because of its high relevance as a real-life communicative task in EFL instruction. The high degree of similarity of the three tasks was intended to enable the near-transfer of genre-specific aspects from one text to another. As the short-term intervention took place in one training session only, effects on more general aspects of language proficiency would have been unlikely. For an example writing task, see Supplement A.

After each writing task, students were given feedback designed according to the condition they had been randomly assigned (see section Measures). The feedback page appeared automatically after the 12 min of writing time had passed or when the student clicked on "Continue." The time spent on the feedback page was user-controlled, so students themselves decided how long they wanted to look at the feedback. A system-controlled minimum of time spent with the feedback may have enhanced treatment fidelity; however, as we wanted to use log data as a measure of behavioral engagement, this was not an option.

The feedback was provided synchronously via an online dashboard by one of six trained human raters based on the rubric (see Fig. 1) and an extensive coding manual (see Supplement B for an example). We calculated the interrater reliability of the six assessors who provided ad-hoc feedback to the students in the experiment to ensure the quality of the provided feedback. As the feedback was based on ordinal scores from 0 to 5, we used Kendalls' W as a non-parametric statistic for rank correlation. The interrater reliability for the six raters in the final round was $W = 0.83$, suggesting that the raters were able to assess the texts reliably on the rubric after the training they had received (for further information on the rater training and evaluation, see Keller et al., 2023). The assigned rater was notified whenever a student had completed a writing task. Raters were required to assign a score (0–5) to position the text on the rubric within 4 min after task completion so that the student could receive immediate feedback. During the assessment procedure, the student was engaged in reading activities.

The raters assessed students' texts using the writing rubric and specifications from a detailed rating manual. The rubric was designed hierarchically, so each step included mastery of the steps below. The rubric focused on surface genre features of formal email writing and was directed at the writing product submitted by the students. Each text was assigned to a level on the rubric, specifying what criteria had already been met. The hierarchical illustration of the writing rubric, as shown in Fig. 1, was presented to the students as feedback.

3.3. Measures

3.3.1. Experimental conditions

Students were randomly assigned to four experimental conditions with varying degrees of feedback information (see Table 1). In each condition, including the control group (CG), students were provided with self-study material in the form of an instructional manual for email writing (see Supplement C). Additionally, the first experimental group (EG1; transparency information) received the general email writing rubric (see Fig. 1) without indicating what step had been reached. In reference to the rubric, the other two experimental groups were provided with evaluative feedback in the form of the level of their current text (EG2; individual performance information) and the next level to aspire (EG3; individual performance improvement information), respectively. In addition to the visual information on individual performance presented via an arrow in the rubric (see Fig. 1), both EG2 and EG3 were provided with textual information on the steps that had been reached. For example: "How are you going? Your last email reached Step 1. This means that your email contained all the information required in the task". In addition, EG3 was provided with information on how to proceed: "Where to next? Keep it up, and in your next email, try to choose a salutation and closing that are adequate to the situation described in the task. Keep in mind the elements of a formal email and the associated tone to move to the next level. Use the information from the "checklist," which is presented below the assessment criteria."

3.3.2. Dependent variables

Writing Performance. Three task-feedback cycles were implemented, with the first text representing the baseline measurement (initial performance) and the third text depicting performance development as a function of the intervention (final performance). The whole text corpus was scored based on the rubric (see Fig. 1) and a coding manual (see Supplement B) by two independent raters after the end of the experimental study. These ratings were categorical, as each criterion was coded individually (0/1) to calculate a combined score as holistic measures of initial and final writing performance. Interrater agreement for these post-hoc ratings was satisfactory with Cohen's $\kappa = 0.77$. In cases where the two raters disagreed (14.5%), an adjudicated score was used.

Prior Achievement. Students were asked to indicate the English grade from their last report card. The self-reported grade was used to

Fig. 1. Hierarchical instructional rubric used for providing feedback on genre-specific aspects of formal email writing
 Note: Translated from German into English.

Table 1
 Experimental conditions and information provided.

Condition	Feedback information	Self-study material	Rubric (TI)	Current level (IPI)	Next step (IPII)
Control group		X			
Experimental group 1	TI	X	X		
Experimental group 2	TI IPI	X	X	X	
Experimental group 3	TI IPI IPII	X	X	X	X

Note: TI = transparency information; IPI = individual performance information; IPII = individual performance improvement information; X = information provided.

operationalize learners’ prior achievement in their EFL classes. Swiss schools use a 6-point grading scale, where 1 represents the lowest possible grade, and 6 represents the highest possible grade. The mean English grade from the last report card (self-report) in this sample was $M = 4.82$ ($SD = 0.66$).

Behavioral Engagement. Digital learning environments offer the advantage of collecting process data to be used as behavioral measures of feedback engagement (Henrie et al., 2015). LimeSurvey provides insights into student activity logs by indicating how much time they had spent on each page. Thus, we used the total time spent on the feedback pages after students had written and submitted their texts as a measure of their behavioral engagement with the feedback.

3.4. Statistical analyses

A mixed ANOVA was used to check for a priori group differences and to investigate the main effect of time (RQ1). A multilevel linear regression model was used to investigate the effect of each type of feedback information (RQ2) using the linear mixed models function in SPSS. As students were nested within classes, we included classrooms as level 2 to account for the complex data structure. For both dependent variables – performance improvement and behavioral engagement – we simultaneously tested the incremental effects of each type of feedback

information (transparency information, individual performance information, and individual performance improvement information) in reference to the control group. The order of the three writing tasks was included in the model to control for sequence and task difficulty effects using four dummy-coded covariates. We included initial performance as a covariate to predict final performance so that the effects of the experimental conditions could be interpreted as effects on performance improvement (residual change score method). We also tested for moderating effects of prior achievement by including the interaction term of prior achievement and feedback condition in the regression model.

The indirect effect of feedback on performance improvement via time on feedback page (RQ3) was investigated with mediation analysis using the SPSS PROCESS macro by Hayes (2018). The analysis model uses ordinary least squares regression to estimate unstandardized path coefficients for total, direct, and indirect effects; bootstrapping with 5000 samples together with heteroscedasticity consistent standard errors are employed to compute the confidence intervals and inferential statistics (Davidson & MacKinnon, 1993). Effects are considered significant when the confidence interval does not include zero.

4. Results

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for all four conditions. Across conditions, we found that writing performance had improved by

Table 2
 Means, standard deviations and sample sizes for experimental conditions and overall.

	M (SD)			N
	Initial performance	Final performance	Time on feedback page (seconds)	
Control group	1.12 (1.10)	2.04 (1.44)	139.88 (70.30)	85
Experimental group 1	0.94 (0.98)	2.06 (1.62)	124.36 (49.55)	77
Experimental group 2	1.09 (1.16)	2.21 (1.61)	165.57 (74.73)	97
Experimental group 3	1.00 (1.01)	2.19 (1.72)	162.66 (87.50)	79
Overall	1.04 (1.07)	2.13 (1.59)	149.04 (73.70)	338

approximately one level. Whereas students' average initial writing performance was on level 1, the average writing performance was on level 2 in their final text. Time on feedback page shows that, on average, students spent approximately 2.5 min with the feedback.

The mixed ANOVA showed no statistically significant interaction effect of *time*group*, $F(3, 334) = 0.43, ns, d = 0.13$. The main effect of *group* was not significant, meaning that the intervention conditions did not differ in performance per se, $F(3) = 0.28, ns, d = 0.09$. Thus, the randomization in terms of performance can be considered successful. The main effect of *time* on performance was significant and showed a large effect size, $F(1, 334) = 148.36, p < 0.01, d = 1.33$. This finding indicated a general performance improvement with the digital writing tool, independent of the condition (RQ1).

The incremental effects of each kind of feedback information on performance and engagement (RQ2) were analyzed using a multilevel model. The control condition was used as a reference group to control for a general learning-by-doing effect. Including the feedback information in the experimental conditions as dummy-coded predictors allows for an interpretation of each effect as the incremental value of this information. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3. The only statistically significant difference was found for behavioral engagement: Students who received individual performance information spent significantly more time on the feedback page (approximately half a minute longer) than those without this information. Hence, individual rubric-based information on their performance seems to play a crucial role in helping students engage with the feedback. Thus, in the subsequent mediation and moderation analyses, we focus on the effects of individual performance information (EG2/EG3) beyond general, non-individualized information (CG/EG1).

Multilevel linear regression analysis was performed to test for the moderating effect of prior achievement (RQ3). We specified a model that included a dummy variable for individual performance feedback, the self-reported English grade, and the interaction term of the two variables (see Table 4). For performance improvement we found a significant main effect of English grade, indicating that high-achieving students are better able to improve their performance in general. However, there was no interaction of grade with feedback. For behavioral engagement, we found a significant negative interaction effect of feedback and prior achievement. The effect indicates that individual performance feedback is especially beneficial for the engagement of low-achieving students.

To visualize the interaction, we performed a median split of the sample in terms of low-achieving (English grade <5.0) and high-achieving (English grade ≥ 5.0) EFL learners. Fig. 2 shows the time spent with the feedback in the two subgroups, comparing those who

Table 3

Results of a multilevel linear regression analysis for final performance and feedback engagement.

	Final performance ^{a,b}			Behavioral engagement ^a		
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>
Intercept	1.31	0.32	<0.001	135.38	14.76	<0.001
Transparency information	0.16	0.23	0.467	-15.75	10.79	0.145
Individual performance information	0.21	0.23	0.357	41.51	10.45	<0.001
Individual performance improvement information	-0.15	0.24	0.537	-2.76	10.52	0.793

Note. Multilevel models were used to account for the hierarchical structure of the data (students nested within classes); see Table S1 in Supplement D for full model with covariates.

^a Model controlled for task order using four dummy variables as covariates.

^b Model controlled for initial performance (centered) so the coefficients can be interpreted as performance improvement.

Table 4

Results of multilevel linear regression of final performance and behavioral engagement on feedback (individual performance information), previous English grade, and their interaction term.

	Final performance ^{a, b}			Behavioral engagement ^a		
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>
Intercept	1.40	0.29	<0.001	127.35	13.56	<0.001
Feedback	0.25	0.16	0.123	31.21	7.54	<0.001
Grade	0.27	0.11	0.013	6.90	5.17	0.183
Feedback*Grade	0.03	0.16	0.859	-18.92	7.54	0.013

Note. Multilevel models were used to account for the hierarchical structure of the data (students nested within classes); see Table S2 in Supplement D for full model with covariates.

^a Model controlled for task order using four dummy variables as covariates.

^b Model controlled for initial performance (centered) so the coefficients can be interpreted as performance improvement.

Fig. 2. Behavioral engagement of low- and high-achieving students

Note. Time spent with feedback of low- and high-achieving students (median-split according to EFL grades) with and without individual performance feedback.

received individual performance feedback with those who did not. It shows that – even though individual performance feedback leads to higher behavioral engagement in both groups – the effect is larger for the low-achieving subgroup. Thus, low-achieving students benefit even more from individual performance information than high-achieving students.

Based on the significant positive effect of individual performance feedback on behavioral engagement (see Table 3), we investigated the question of whether behavioral engagement may be a relevant mediator for individual performance feedback to predict performance improvement. Mediation analysis was performed to analyze whether there was an indirect effect of individual performance information on writing performance improvement via behavioral engagement (see Fig. 3). The analysis showed that individual performance feedback predicted engagement significantly, $a = 0.49, p < 0.001$, which in turn predicted

Fig. 3. Mediation of the effect of individual performance feedback on performance improvement via behavioral engagement (time spent with feedback).

writing performance improvement significantly, $b = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$. The direct effect of feedback on performance improvement in the mediation model was not significant, $c' = 0.06$, *ns*. The indirect effect shows that the relationship between feedback and writing performance improvement was mediated by behavioral engagement, $ab = 0.15$, 95%-CI[0.06, 0.28].

5. Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the effects of rubric-based feedback on the EFL writing performance of eighth-grade students, with a particular emphasis on the mediating role of behavioral engagement. In the following section, we will summarize the principal findings in relation to our expectations and discuss the limitations and educational ramifications of this research.

5.1. Summary

As expected, students' writing performance improved substantially, moving from an average level of 1 (i.e., the basic level of achievement according to our hierarchical email writing model) to a level of 2 after the intervention. This suggests that in general, self-regulated writing practice with a digital tool can positively impact EFL students' writing performance. Contrary to our expectations, however, the feedback types used in this study did not show the expected differential effects on performance. Of the different types of information, only individual performance information showed an incremental effect on behavioral engagement. Thus, students who received an individual evaluation of their current performance spent more time with the feedback than those who were presented with non-individualized information, i. e., who worked only with the general learning material and the rubric. Further analyses showed that low-achieving EFL students, in particular, benefited from feedback on their performance. This finding was in line with our expectations. Their engagement with the feedback was higher when they received individual performance information, whereas the effect was less pronounced for high-achieving students. However, further research is needed to investigate the effects of (different types of) feedback on different levels of achievement.

While there was no direct effect of individual performance feedback on performance improvement, there was a significant indirect effect mediated by behavioral engagement, again in line with our expectations. Thus, presenting students with individualized feedback was superior to providing general information like learning material or assessment rubrics, indicating an incremental effect of individualized feedback only when students spend enough time with it. This finding highlights the importance of how students interact with feedback, reminding us that it is not just the presence of certain types of information that has an impact, but how students engage with it.

5.2. Limitations

This study was conducted with eighth- and ninth-grade students from North-Western Switzerland, limiting its generalizability. Furthermore, it centers on formal email writing in English as a foreign language, one facet of a broader set of writing skills relevant to the curricula at this educational level. Extending the study across different age groups and cultural settings would be necessary to assess the degree to which our findings are transferrable to other settings. Future research would also need to compare the effects of rubric-based feedback across different writing genres (e. g., reports or simple argumentative texts; [Siekman et al., 2023](#)).

The feedback effects found in this study were relatively small, and the differences in performance improvement between the conditions were not significant. Several aspects of the intervention procedure could explain this finding: First, the writing tool in this study was used for a short time period in one training session only. Therefore, the lack of

differential effects may also be due to the short duration of the intervention. It could be argued that students benefit more from such feedback if they work with it regularly. Investigating the long-term impacts of such feedback interventions on students' writing abilities would be an interesting extension of this research. Second, the feedback provided in the intervention was rather minimal. Students were presented with feedback on each text they wrote. Even though there were different types of feedback, the information provided in all groups was brief and somewhat limited. There was no tutorial information included in the feedback; it was merely a performance assessment that could be related to the general learning material. Thus, students may not have had the information necessary to improve their performance. Third, the students were not required to revise their texts but produced new ones in each round. In future studies, it would be desirable to measure revision performance (in addition to transfer performance) as a more direct response to the intervention in order to understand the full potential of the feedback. Fourth, another explanation for why we did not find differential intervention effects could be that all groups (including the control condition) were provided self-learning material (i.e., a short guide to writing emails) that already included much of the required information on improving their writing. This material alone might have helped learners to improve their texts and may thus have masked any differential feedback effects. The additional information that was presented by the rubric and the individual performance feedback may even have conflicted with the effective use of this information rather than supported it. All of these reasons combined may explain the non-significant differences between the conditions, but more research is needed to understand the necessary prerequisites of feedback effectiveness.

Engagement is a multi-dimensional construct, including cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects. However, in the present study, we measured only behavioral engagement. In future studies, we would include other facets of engagement to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the feedback reception process. Behavioral engagement was operationalized as the time spent on the feedback page, limiting the interpretability of the findings. As we cannot know what students did while spending time with the feedback, we do not know what cognitive or affective processes were key to its effectiveness. Further studies are necessary to test more specific hypotheses concerning engagement.

Similarly, the operationalization of prior achievement by self-reported English grades could be improved. Using self-reported grades as achievement measures can be problematic for two reasons: (a) The reliability of self-reports may not be sufficient, and (b) teachers' judgments may not be valid and objective measures of actual skills. However, there is some evidence suggesting that self-reported grades may be a relevant indicator of students' achievement. [Sticca et al. \(2017\)](#) conducted a study to examine the accuracy of students' self-reported academic grades in a very similar sample: Lower secondary education (year 9) students in the German-speaking cantons of Switzerland. They compared the students' self-reported grades in different subjects (mathematics, German, English, French) with those reported by the school administration. They found a very high correlation of $r = 0.91$ between self-reported and actual English grades. The authors conclude that self-reported grades are sufficiently accurate to be used as indicators of actual grades in educational research.

So, while the reliability of students' self-reported grades seems high, their validity and objectivity are questionable. On the one hand, teachers' grades capture several factors apart from actual performance (e.g., personality, e.g., [Hübner et al., 2022](#); [Meyer et al., 2023](#); motivation; e.g., [Meyer et al., 2019](#)) and are prone to judgment bias and reference group effects ([Hübner et al., 2020](#); [Neumann et al., 2011](#)). Thus, we cannot be sure they are a true measure of students' domain-specific skills. On the other hand, meta-analytical research has found teachers' judgments to be correlated with actual test performance ($r = 0.63$; [Südkamp et al., 2012](#)) as well as school grades to be correlated with later achievement ($r = 0.53$; [Trapmann et al., 2007](#)).

However, even though there are indicators of the validity of grades,

interpreting a “grade effect” as a “prior knowledge effect” is not advisable. Therefore, the findings on prior achievement (i.e., the self-reported English grade) as a moderator of behavioral engagement should be interpreted cautiously. However, we argue that our findings are relevant enough to motivate further research into the role of interindividual differences in students’ processing and uptake of feedback. Future studies should include standardized proficiency measures or a writing test to enhance our understanding of the differential effects of feedback. Furthermore, interindividual variables such as typing fluency or prior experience with computer-based writing were not measured. These could also be relevant moderators of feedback effectiveness that should be investigated in further research, using self-reports as well as key log data.

A related limitation of the current study is that we cannot provide information on the writing instruction students have received beforehand. Collecting information on students’ general writing skills and task-specific knowledge would be advisable in future studies. Moreover, an experimental manipulation of task-specific writing instruction would be an interesting way of investigating the prior knowledge effect more directly by comparing the feedback uptake of students who have received an instruction intervention to those who have not.

5.3. Implications for research and practice

Our findings do not concur with the initial assumption that individual performance *improvement* information is key to successful feedback implementation (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Wollenschläger et al., 2016). On the contrary, the question of “How am I going?” in the feedback model by Hattie and Timperley (2007) seems to be the most relevant in the context of this study. Thus, the theoretical assumption that feedback messages need to address all feedback questions and that the information on the next step is most crucial does not hold in this case. Here, the positive effect of individual performance feedback has been exhausted by informing the learners of their current performance in relation to a rubric. By building on the general information provided in a rubric and the individual performance information, students may be able to answer the third question of where to go next themselves. Moreover, the effects of feedback are relatively small compared to the general effect of practicing with non-individualized learning material. These findings are in line with current developments in feedback theory, advocating for a more complex and interactional view of feedback effectiveness (Lipnevich & Panadero, 2021; Panadero & Lipnevich, 2021): Feedback never occurs in isolation and simply focusing on the feedback message to determine its effectiveness is insufficient. Feedback research and theory need to consider the complexity of the feedback process and take into account the needs of different learners and the interaction of students with the feedback (Lipnevich & Smith, 2022). Furthermore, the feedback process should not be considered in isolation; instead, the interplay of feedback, (strategy) instruction, and practice should be considered to better understand and model learning processes (Graham et al., 2024).

Our findings are in line with recent findings on computer-based feedback that show comparably small effects for students in lower secondary education (Mertens et al., 2022; Ngo et al., 2022; Zhai & Ma, 2022). In a very similar context, Siekmann et al. (2023) could not find significant feedback effects on text quality in an intervention study with less proficient EFL writers. Possible explanations for the lack of feedback effects in lower secondary or low proficiency contexts are that (a) the demands of the feedback exceed the cognitive resources of younger students (Fyfe et al., 2015; Sweller et al., 1998) and (b) their prior domain knowledge and semantic networks are not developed enough to successfully interpret and integrate new information or material (Brod et al., 2013; Hoffman, 2019; Shing & Brod, 2016). Further studies should focus on how feedback can be presented in a way that is more accommodating and engaging for lower secondary students. These studies should consider the students’ judgments of feedback usefulness and its

effect on performance to gain a more holistic understanding of the feedback reception process.

Findings also imply that behavioral engagement appears to be a critical driver in utilizing feedback effectively. The mediation effect underpins the importance of the feedback mechanism, emphasizing the interplay between feedback type and student engagement. These findings align with more recent models that see engagement with feedback as a central variable in the feedback reception process (Fong & Schallert, 2023; Panadero, 2013). Future research should zoom in on this process, investigating students’ engagement and its effect on performance improvement in more detail. Moreover, interventions that aim to enhance feedback engagement are necessary to provide evidence of the conditions necessary for effective feedback.

Teachers and educators should be trained to provide feedback that identifies areas of improvement and is designed to engage students actively. The use of rubrics and well-structured learning material, as seen in this study, can be an effective tool in this regard. Furthermore, with relatively little effort, teachers can use summative rubric-based scores for formative assessment purposes. As individual performance feedback was found to lead to higher engagement, a teacher’s assessment will likely benefit the students’ learning process – especially for those who are not doing well anyway. A carefully constructed rubric is a helpful basis for providing timely and understandable feedback to the students. Alongside teacher training, it may be beneficial to train students on how to effectively engage with and use feedback. As the study indicates, the mere provision of feedback is insufficient – its efficacy depends on student engagement.

6. Conclusion

In sum, this study highlights that the effectiveness of individualized feedback is intertwined with the degree of student engagement. The individual evaluation of a student’s written work may not improve performance if the student does not engage with the feedback appropriately. Therefore, student engagement requires more attention in feedback research and educational practice.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Johanna Fleckenstein: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Thorben Jansen:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Jennifer Meyer:** Writing – review & editing. **Ruth Trüb:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Emily E. Raubach:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Stefan D. Keller:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2024.101977>.

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